

Sign Language-Controlled Robot: A Simple and Time-Efficient Approach to Human-Machine Interaction

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Figure 1: Graphical Abstract

ABSTRACT

Machine learning has played an important role in sign language recognition over the past decade. However, many existing systems are complex, require extensive computational power, and lack precision in real-time use. This project aims to develop a simple and time-efficient sign language-controlled robot that interprets static American Sign Language (ASL) gestures to perform movement-based tasks. Built with a Raspberry Pi, the robot will communicate with a nearby laptop to detect and classify signs in real time. Building on prior research, this project will use innovative computer vision techniques for static sign recognition. It will focus on improving static sign detection accuracy while minimizing latency, enhancing overall system responsiveness. The study highlights the potential of sign language for human-machine interaction, with broader applications in accessibility and inclusion.

Keywords: Neural Network, Deep Learning, Computer Vision, Raspberry Pi, Robotics, Sign Language

1 INTRODUCTION

Human-machine interaction (HMI) is a rapidly evolving field that bridges the gap between humans and technology, enabling intuitive communication and control of machines. As technology becomes more integrated into daily life, effective HMI systems are crucial for making technology accessible to a wide range of users. One promising approach to HMI is gesture recognition, which allows users to interact with machines through natural and intuitive movements. This method eliminates the need for traditional interfaces like keyboards or touchscreens, making it particularly valuable in scenarios where hands-free or remote operation is necessary.

Gesture-based HMI systems have transformative potential across numerous fields. In healthcare, they can enable surgeons to control medical devices during operations without physical contact, reducing the risk of contamination. Similarly, in industrial applications, workers can control machinery in hazardous environments without direct contact, increasing safety and efficiency.

However, despite their promise, gesture recognition systems face key challenges. Real-time recognition of complex, dynamic gestures remains difficult due to variations in hand shapes, motion speeds, and environmental lighting conditions. Additionally, accurately mapping these gestures to machine commands often requires complex computational models and face latency problems. These challenges limit the reliability and practicality of gesture-based interfaces in real-world applications. This project aims to address these challenges by developing a simple and low-latency gesture-controlled robot capable of interpreting static American Sign Language (ASL) gestures. Using innovative computer vision techniques and a Raspberry Pi-based robot, the system will recognize and perform tasks based on signs performed in a time-efficient manner. This advancement will contribute to the broader adoption of HMI technology in accessibility and robotics, creating a more inclusive, efficient, and human-centered approach to human-machine interaction.

2 RELATED WORK

Controlling a robot without explicitly using a remote controller can be achieved in multiple ways. Among them, control via voice commands and hand gestures is promising. A lot of research has

been done in voice detection and recognition, and although significant research has also been done in hand gesture recognition, there is still much to be explored in the field of sign language detection. Effective gesture recognition is foundational for a sign language-controlled robot. Studies have explored ways to recognize hand gestures, especially in the context of sign language recognition. One main challenge many researchers have identified is the complexity and diversity of signs in American Sign Language (ASL). Many signs are static, while others are dynamic. Additionally, many dynamic signs look very similar under different angles making them difficult to distinguish.

2.1 Common Approaches for Static Signs Recognition

Many studies have investigated static sign recognition and achieved high accuracy. Barbhuiya et al. (2021) focused on static gesture recognition using pre-trained AlexNet and VGG16 models. Features extracted from the ImageNet dataset were then classified using a support vector machine (SVM), yielding high accuracy in static sign recognition. While Barbhuiya et al. (2021) only used RGB channels in the images to train their neural network, Kuznetsova et al. (2013) highlighted the role of depth cameras in capturing detailed hand gesture features from static hand signs. Their approach utilizes a multi-layered random forest model, taking advantage of depth information in the image to classify each sign. Their model input is a 3D point cloud, which they first cluster to group similar classes together. The first random forest (RF) layer classifies each cluster of similar signs, and the second layer classifies each sign within each cluster. This alternative method to CNNs also achieves good accuracy with low training time. However, similar to Barbhuiya et al. (2021), their experiment is only valid for static images.

2.2 Two Streams Networks

Other methods combining various features of a single image have been investigated and have yielded even better results for static signs. Specifically, Dadashzadeh et al. (2020) proposed a two-stage fusion network, taking advantage of the appearance of an image (RGB color channel) and the segmentation map of the sign. The image is first transformed into a segmentation map, delimiting the hand performing the sign, and then two CNNs are fed with the segmented gesture map and its RGB appearance, respectively. Their outputs are combined at the decision level using summation techniques to produce the final classification. Similarly, Xu et al. (2014) took advantage of depth information to delimit the hand and then used the RGB color channel for skin color detection. Combining depth and RGB features yielded more accurate results than using just one channel.

The previous studies highlight the role of depth cameras as well as regular RGB cameras in recognizing sign languages. Combining these streams of information yields even better results, according to Dadashzadeh et al. (2020) and Xu et al. (2014). This approach allows them to overcome issues such as similar skin and background colors as well as lighting problems. This innovative approach of cleverly combining various streams of information deserves more exploration, as there are various ways to fuse them—at the decision level, feature level, or data level. Additionally, each of the individual

streams can have many different architectures, leaving room to explore creative designs and combinations to achieve better results in static sign classification.

2.3 Dynamic Signs Recognition

While a great amount of work has been done in static sign detection, there is still room for improvement, especially in dynamic sign detection. In the quest to recognize larger amounts of signs in ASL, including dynamic signs, researchers have confronted issues such as detecting when a dynamic sign starts and ends. It is crucial to have a rough idea of the window in which the sign occurs. If it is inaccurate, one sign may look too different and be classified as another sign. In addition, it is essential to make sense of the relationship between each frame in a dynamic sign. There is a logical order between each frame that must be considered to achieve high accuracy.

2.4 3D CNNs

Considering the relationship between each frame in a dynamic sign, researchers developed a new type of CNN to add an extra dimension of time. They are called 3D CNNs, in contrast to conventional 2D CNNs, based on the number of input dimensions they can handle. Li et al. (2020) and Kopuklu et al. (2019) leveraged 3D CNNs to address the problem of the time dimension in dynamic sign detection. On testing data, they achieved high accuracy, seemingly addressing the problem of detecting dynamic signs. However, in a real environment, it is crucial to know when a sign is being performed to efficiently pass the specific frames to the 3D CNN for sign classification.

Addressing the issue of knowing the starting and ending points of a sign, Xu et al. (2014) used a specific static gesture to mark these points. This approach allowed them to use previous work on static gesture recognition to show when a dynamic sign starts and ends. While promising, this approach does not explicitly solve the problem of detecting the ending and starting points of a dynamic sign. To address this, Kopuklu et al. (2019) trained a 3D CNN to infer when a sign is being performed. They used a sliding window approach, with 8 frames fed to their 3D CNN to detect if a movement is being performed. This way, Kopuklu et al. (2019) could detect when a dynamic sign is being performed and use a set number of frames to classify the exact sign being made.

2.5 Limits of 3D CNNs

While innovative and promising, 3D CNNs require extensive amounts of data to train. Since they are used to recognize video patterns, which involve more data than regular images, they need to learn more complex models. As a result, training them requires extensive computational power and the large size of 3D CNNs limits their use in real-time applications to powerful devices, making them largely inaccessible to many users.

2.6 Application to Robotics

Overall, in the context of creating a robot controlled by sign language, there appears to be little work done in various ways. Most of the work focused solely on recognizing hand gestures or sign language without applying it to robots, which is the goal of this paper. After reviewing the current state of the field, there appear

to be two main areas for improvement. The first is the possibility of combining RGB and depth image information at different stages and in innovative ways to achieve higher accuracy in static sign classification. Second, there is a need to implement a simple, low-latency, real-time sign recognition system that enables a robot to interpret and perform tasks based on sign language instructions. This paper investigates these two aspects as they are interconnected and both crucial for advancing the field.

3 METHODOLOGY

The proposed system comprises two primary components: the sign recognition system and the robot. All individuals included in the datasets and those who volunteered to test the system gave their consent to participate and were informed of the research purpose.

3.1 Dataset

In this project, three different datasets were used to train the model as it was important to increase the variety of the images to achieve higher accuracies. The first one was found on the internet, the second one was created for this project by the author and the third was a mix of both.

The first dataset, found on the internet, is the American Sign Language (ASL) Alphabet dataset publicly available on Kaggle. It contains 87,000 images of hand gestures representing the 26 letters of the English alphabet. As Figure 2 shows, the images were captured under various lighting conditions and orientations, mostly with white backgrounds. Four signs in this dataset were selected for the sake of this project, which indicate the four possible directions the robot can move. Specifically, the letter L represents the left direction, R the right direction, N the north direction (forward), and S the south direction (backward). These signs were chosen because they have a dual meaning: the letter itself and a direction. Hence, out of all 87,000 images only 8,000 images were selected, which constitute my base dataset for the model. Finally, data augmentation, such as rotations, flipping, and brightness adjustments, was applied to increase the variety within this dataset, allowing the model to generalize well. These transformations were carefully selected to preserve the general shape of the signs. Excessive rotation could create ambiguity by resembling a different sign or altering its meaning. Since sign language is precise and orientation-sensitive, only limited data augmentation was used to maintain the integrity of each gesture.

As shown in Figure 3, the second dataset, created for this project, differs from the first one due to the variety of background colors, patterns, and lighting conditions. Including greater environmental diversity was essential to enable the model to achieve high accuracy regardless of the background. This dataset consisted of a total of 160 images, with 40 images per category. As with the first dataset, each category represents a direction the robot can follow. To make the dataset more suitable for training, its size was increased through careful data augmentation techniques similar to the first dataset. The final augmented dataset contained 640 images, with 160 images per category.

Lastly, the third dataset was a mix of both the dataset from Kaggle and the one created for this project. Each of the four classes had the same number of images, 80, for a total of 320 for the entire

Figure 2: Sample images of Kaggle dataset

Figure 3: Sample images of my dataset

mixed dataset. Within each class there are 40 images from the self made dataset and 40 images from the Kaggle dataset. Balancing the number of images per class was essential to avoid bias and overfitting, while also ensuring the dataset was a representative mix of both sources. The purpose of creating this mixed dataset was to compare the model's performance across different dataset compositions.

Finally, before training, the images of both datasets were resized to 150x150 pixels, and the pixel values were normalized between -1 and 1. This ensured that the model received the same data shape for each image and also contributed to increasing the accuracy of the model.

3.2 Pre-trained Models

Importing pre-trained Models appeared to be the best solution to achieve good performance as their architectures were specifically made for edge detection. They also already perform well on classification tasks containing hundreds of categories and they are good at detecting patterns in image recognition. In addition extensive datasets and computational resources are required to train such models to achieve good performance. For these reasons, I chose to import pre-trained models with their weights trained on the imagenet dataset, assuring a minimal good accuracy. Specifically, vGG16 and DenseNet201 pre-trained were chosen for my classification tasks. VGG16 was chosen for its strong features extraction capabilities and high classification task accuracy. On the other

hand, DenseNet201 was chosen for its efficiency in complex image processing tasks as well as its computational efficiency, making it perfect for real-time applications.

3.3 Hybrid Fusion of DenseNet201 and VGG16

Various approaches using these pre-trained models were tried to obtain the best accuracy under different conditions and environments. The selected method consists of fusing the outputs of two pre-trained models at an intermediate stage, taking advantage of their individual strengths.

3.3.1 DenseNet201 Architecture.

Figure 4 shows the general DenseNet architecture. It is a deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) consisting of four dense blocks, where each layer receives inputs from all previous layers. DenseNet201 specifically contains 201 layers, making it deeper and potentially more powerful for complex feature extraction.

Figure 4: DenseNet Architecture: A Deep CNN with 201 Layers Divided in 4 blocks

3.3.2 VGG16 Architecture.

Figure 5 shows the architecture of VGG16. It is a deep learning model with 16 layers, structured into five convolutional blocks that extract image features step by step. Unlike DenseNet201, which uses global average pooling, VGG16 flattens the feature maps before passing them through three fully connected layers, making it computationally heavier but effective for classification tasks.

Figure 5: VGG-16 Architecture: A Deep CNN with 16 Layers, Including Convolutional, Max-Pooling and Fully Connected Layers

Both models were imported with the classification layers truncated and instead adding dense and dropout layers.

3.3.3 Fusion Architecture.

Leveraging the strengths of both architectures, I implemented a hybrid fusion model that combines highly abstracted features extracted by DenseNet201 and VGG16. First, each model processes the input image separately, extracting high-level features through their respective layers. Both models generate a compact feature representation of the input, reducing dimensionality while preserving essential information.

Next, the extracted features are concatenated to form a unified feature vector. To refine this fusion, an attention mechanism is applied, learning the importance of each feature and enhancing the most relevant ones. Finally, the fused feature representation passes through a fully connected layer for classification, ensuring that the combined model benefits from DenseNet201's efficient feature reuse and VGG16's deep hierarchical representations.

This hybrid fusion technique differs from decision and feature-level fusion in its approach to combining information from multiple models. Feature-level fusion directly merges features extracted by each model before classification. On the other hand, decision-level fusion combines the final predictions made by each model. In my model, hybrid fusion occurs at an intermediate stage, after passing through specific layers but before final decision-making. An attention mechanism is then used to refine and weigh the features, allowing the model to take advantage of the complementary strengths of each model. This technique proved to work and achieve high accuracies on both datasets.

3.3.4 Training Specifications.

The model was trained using the RMSprop optimizer, which is a derived version of the Adam optimizer, with categorical cross-entropy loss, employing a batch size of 32 and an initial learning rate of 0.001. Early stopping and learning rate reduction were applied to prevent overfitting and optimize convergence.

3.4 Data Framework

Integrating my sign language classification model into the robot computer system was crucial to minimizing latency between the two systems.

The robot is made of a Raspberry Pi and thus cannot support the classification model due to its limited computational capabilities. The model runs on a nearby laptop with sufficient computational capacities to avoid this problem. The robot broadcasts a private wifi connection, and the laptop connects to it. It allows the two devices to communicate and send back-and-forth data between the two devices. The TCP/IP protocol is used with the robot running a server and waiting for a connection from the laptop (client). The robot is set to listen on a specific port, and the laptop sends requests via a client socket. Once the communication is established, the computer and robot can exchange data with low latency within a few meters range.

The robot has a camera mounted on top and sends frames to the connected laptop. Once received, the laptop collects a set number of frames in a buffer and selects the least blurry one to pass to the classification model for sign prediction. Once a prediction is made, the buffer is flushed, and the output is returned to the robot, which moves accordingly. This process is repeated for multiple sign predictions. An extra module, in addition to the Raspberry Pi, is added to control the individual motors of the robot, facilitating movement based on the predicted sign. Figure 6 shows the data flow between the different components of this system.

Figure 6: Data Flow Architecture

4 RESULTS

4.1 Training Results

The three models proposed (VGG16, DenseNet201, and VGG16 x DenseNet201 Fused) were trained on the three datasets proposed in the methods section. Table 1 shows how each model performs on their respective training and validation datasets. VGG16 is optimal on *My Images* dataset, achieving 96% accuracy. On the other hand, DenseNet201 is optimal on *Kaggle Dataset*, with 98% accuracy. Overall, this means that individual pre-trained models perform well on these datasets and can recognize general patterns within them. However, their accuracy drops significantly when these pre-trained models are tested on datasets other than those they were trained on. Table 2 shows that VGG16, trained on *My*

Images dataset, achieves only 47% accuracy on *Kaggle Dataset*. Similarly, DenseNet201, trained on *Kaggle Dataset*, achieves only 57% accuracy on *My Images* dataset. It clearly demonstrates how these two individual models struggle to generalize their results. They perform well when classifying images similar to those they were trained on but struggle when encountering different images.

The fusion model better generalizes the results learned from one dataset to another. It is due to its architecture taking advantage of the strength of each individual pre-trained, making it easier to learn general patterns and not focus on the background. Table 2 shows how the fusion model performs well even when the validation dataset differs from the dataset it was trained on. When it is trained on *My Images* dataset, it achieves an accuracy of 78% on *Kaggle Dataset*, against 47% achieved by VGG16. Similarly, when the fusion model is trained on *Kaggle Dataset* and tested with *My Images* dataset, it achieves an accuracy of 82% against 57% achieved by DenseNet201. Although not perfect, the accuracy achieved by the fusion model is better than the individual pre-trained model, showing that they can learn more complex patterns and generalize them.

Model	Training and Validation Dataset	Accuracy
VGG16	My Images	0.96
-	Kaggle Dataset	0.97
DenseNet201	My Images	0.91
-	Kaggle Dataset	0.98
Fusion	My Images	0.82
-	Kaggle Dataset	0.97
-	Mixed Dataset	0.91

Table 1: Training performance of VGG16, DenseNet201, and Fusion models.

Model	Training Dataset	Validation Dataset	Accuracy
VGG16	My Images	Kaggle Dataset	0.47
-	My Images	Mixed Dataset	0.74
-	Kaggle Dataset	My Images	0.60
-	Kaggle Dataset	Mixed Dataset	0.74
DenseNet201	My Images	Kaggle Dataset	0.49
-	My Images	Mixed Dataset	0.74
-	Kaggle Dataset	My Images	0.57
-	Kaggle Dataset	Mixed Dataset	0.71
Fusion	My Images	Kaggle Dataset	0.78
-	My Images	Mixed Dataset	0.74
-	Kaggle Dataset	My Images	0.82
-	Kaggle Dataset	Mixed Dataset	0.91
-	Mixed Dataset	My Images	0.80
-	Mixed Dataset	Kaggle Dataset	0.95

Table 2: Cross-dataset evaluation of VGG16 and DenseNet201.

4.2 Live Classification

4.2.1 Classification.

The previous tables show encouraging results and performance from the different models developed. Testing live classification in various environments, with multiple backgrounds and various people performing the signs, is also crucial. Live classification matters more than validation tests, as the robot will not always be in the same environment, and the goal is to adapt to different environments and users.

After performing 80 signs across various backgrounds and people performing them, 56 were correctly predicted, resulting in an accuracy of 70%. It is about 10% lower than expected based on the cross-validation accuracy. Nonetheless, this accuracy is still promising, as it provides better results than random guessing, which would achieve an accuracy of 25%.

Table 3 shows the prediction distribution across the four classes. The sign South is the most recognized one, followed by Left and Right. Apart from the sign North, they all achieved decent, more than satisfying, scores. Its low score of 50% shows that the model struggles to recognize it. This might be due to confusion with the sign Right, as both are similar in that two fingers—the index and the middle finger—are extended upward or downward and separated from the rest of the hand.

	Incorrectly Predicted	Correctly Predicted	Success %
Left	5	15	75.0%
North	10	10	50.0%
Right	6	14	70.0%
South	3	17	85.0%

Table 3: Live classification performance using the fusion model.

4.2.2 Skin Color Considerations.

After training the model on datasets primarily composed of images of white people’s hands, it is essential to evaluate how it performs with individuals of different skin tones. Among the 10 people who volunteered to test the system, two had non-white, tan/light brown skin tones. Table 4 shows the model’s performance specifically on the two non-white participants.

	Incorrectly Predicted	Correctly Predicted	Success %
Left	2	2	50.0%
North	3	1	25.0%
Right	2	2	50.0%
South	1	3	75.0%

Table 4: Live classification performance using the fusion model on non-white skin color.

Although the system shows slightly lower performance on non-white skin tones, the results are acceptable, achieving an overall accuracy of 50%, which is still better than random guessing. The same patterns as in Table 3 appear: the sign South is the most recognized one, followed by Left and Right, while the model still struggles to recognize the sign North. The brightness and contrast adjustments applied to the images in the dataset help the model

generalize what it learns on non-white skin tones. However, further refinement is needed to achieve better accuracy on non-white skin tones by adding improved data augmentation or expanding the dataset.

4.2.3 Latency.

Another key parameter to consider is the overall latency of the system. Over 100 classifications, the mean time it took the fusion model to make its prediction was 0.24 seconds. Given that the model was run on an average laptop with no additional or high-end computational resources, and considering the size of the model, an average prediction time of 0.24 seconds is good.

The total time to run all 100 predictions was 4.23 minutes. It includes capturing the frame, sending it to the computer, calculating the output, sending the result back to the robot, and the robot performing the movement. On average, the entire process for one prediction, including both communication and computation, took 2.63 seconds.

This timing is acceptable given the computational resources used, a nearby laptop. It demonstrates that effective real-time interaction can be achieved even with accessible to everyone hardware. The response time is sufficient for addressing real-world problems in accessibility-focused applications, where simplicity and user experience is essential. Applied to daily task a response time under three second is sufficient and could be further improved if needed.

5 FUTURE WORK

The completion of this project advanced the field of human-computer interaction and sign language detection. Various CNN architectures were tested, and the fusion model proved to be the most accurate, versatile, and time-efficient. It can adapt to different environments and hand colors, and requires fairly small computational resources, making it ideal for real-world applications in accessibility or automation.

Important progress was made through this project, but significant work is yet to be done. It would be interesting to develop a model that is more accurate across all classes and minimizes accuracy discrepancies between them. A more comprehensive dataset including diverse backgrounds and a wider range of hand colors would be essential for improving generalization and overall accuracy. Additionally, extending the number of classes and increasing the complexity of tasks performed by the robot would be valuable. For example, incorporating more complex dynamic signs and enhancing the robot’s functionality by integrating sensors could enable it to pick up objects or even navigate autonomously in its environment.

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